

Xanthogranulomatous Pituitary Endocrine Tumor Associated to Pituitary Apoplex. Case report

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ABSTRACT

Xanthogranulomatous pituitary adenoma is relatively rare disease, therefore, the etiology, diagnosis, management, and prognosis of this disorder remain partly understood. Accurate diagnosis of xanthogranulomatous pituitary adenoma is based on histopathological criteria.

We reported the case of a 55-year-old male patient who presented intermittent visual disturbance and headache, a chiasmatic syndrome was diagnosed. Brain magnetic resonance imaging revealed a sellar mass with a heterogeneous signal. Transsphenoidal surgery was performance, and the mass was suborally resected, and histopathological examination established the diagnosis of granulomatous pituitary neuroendocrine tumor (Pitnet) and apoplexy. The etiology, the pathogenesis of Xanthogranuloma of the sellar region (XSR) remains incompletely understood but the main hypothesis that Xanthogranuloma (XG) could occur as an inflammatory response secondary to the rupture and hemorrhage of a previous cystic process, there by producing an expansion of the tumor body toward adjacent tissues. One study proposed that xanthogranulomas may develop secondary to hemorrhage, inflammation, or degeneration or may be is due to apoplexy changes.

Keywords: Xanthogranulomatous pituitary adenoma; Pituitary neuroendocrine tumor (Pitnet); Pituitary apoplexy

ABBREVIATION

Xanthogranuloma (XG); Xanthogranulomatous pituitary adenoma (XPA); Pituitary neuroendocrine tumor (Pitnet); Pituitary apoplexy (PA); Xanthogranuloma of the sellar region (XSR); Xanthogranulomatous change (XGCs); Adamantinomatous Craniopharyngioma (AdaCP); Papillary craniopharyngioma (PCP); Xanthomatous hypophysitis (XH); Rathke's cleft cysts (RCC)

INTRODUCTION

Xanthogranuloma (XG) is a pathological entity of unknown origin but is thought to result from a process of chronic inflammation due to findings in histology which include macrophage infiltration, central necrosis, multinucleated giant cells and hemosiderin deposition, change should be carefully assessed in adenomas.^[1] The skin or eye and other peripheral sites are the most frequent, they rarely develop intracranially occurring in 1.6%-7% associated to pituitary adenoma (PA),^[2,3] and only a few case reports and series describe xanthogranulomas developing in the parasellar or sellar regions. Also, XG, due to the most likely origin, sellar xanthogranuloma, is also referred to as cholesterol granuloma or xanthogranulomatous reaction.

The xanthogranulomatous change (XGCs) was first described in 1988 in only 4 of 211 sellar tumors.^[4] They were conventionally classified as a variant of Adamantinomatous craniopharyngioma (AdaCP), as they both share cholesterol clefts, even in the absence of epithelial tissue, In 1999, Paulus et al.^[5] described 37 tumors with a predominating xanthogranulomatous component of 110 craniopharyngiomas (CPs) with massive cholesterol reaction, non-adamantinomatous squamous epithelium, or missing epithelium, a predominant intrasellar location, with favorable outcome, among intracranial lesions. Suggesting xanthogranuloma (cholesterol granuloma) of the sellar region is clinically and pathologically distinct from the classical adamantinomatous craniopharyngioma. Finally, xanthogranuloma, has been defined as an isolated entity by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2000.^[3]

Xanthogranuloma of the sellar region (XSR) is a rare disease and have traditionally divided into two separate categories, xanthomatous hypophysitis (XH) and xanthogranuloma of the sellar region.^[6] The main clinical manifestations including, visual impairment, headache, and vomiting, chiasmatic syndrome, which starts like any pituitary adenoma, and hypopituitarism including others endocrine abnormalities that unfortunately, may be difficult to resolve, however, sporadic cases have also revealed as obstructive hydrocephalus.^[7] Here, we reported a case of Xanthogranulomatous pituitary adenoma in association to pituitary apoplexy (PA).

CLINICAL CASE

A 55-year-old man, with no significant history, started on April 23, with a sensation of a dull eye, a month later he started with bitemporal heteronymous hemianopia, and intense headache, which is why he came to our institution. Brain magnetic diagnosed as non- functional pituitary neuroendocrine tumor (Pitnet) graded as HV III C (Figure 1). With hemorrhages areas.

At the time of admission, he had hypothyroidism and was treated with levothyroxine. Laboratory tests showed: leukocytes 10,000/mm³, glucose 101 mg/dL, BUN 37 mg/dL, urea 70 mg/dL, uric acid 9 mg/dL, prolactin 55 ng/mL, TSH 0.015 mIU/L, HCG 0,06 mIU/L, ACTH 66 pmol/L, cortisol 10 mcg/dL, glycated hemoglobin 6%, triglycerides 302 mg/dL, fibrinogen 504 mg/dL.

Six months later he was subjected a transnasal transsphenoidal surgery, and intraoperative finding showed an abundant yellowish cheesy creamy material. A yellowish-brown material with a necrotic appearance is received, which it measured 20x18x5mm. Histologically, most of it corresponds to necrosis and hemorrhage, mixed with foci of pituitary neoplasia compatible with adenoma between the areas of necrosis (Figure 2a), cholesterol crystals are observed (Figure 2b), giant multinucleated cells and macrophages (Figure 2c), lymphocytes and hemosiderophages were observed. Immunohistochemistry staining was performed. Foci of pituitary neoplasia were immunopositively reaction to synaptophysin (Figure 2d), and ACTH and were negative to prolactin, ACTH,

Growth hormone, TFH, SH, LH, and pan cytokeratins, EMA, GFAP, vim, and giant multinucleated cells and macrophages were positive to CD68 (Figure 2f). Finally, the diagnosis was pituitary apoplexy within a neuroendocrine pituitary tumor with xanthogranulomatous reaction (XPA).

Figure 1: An extra-axial, bilobed image with defined margins is identified in the sellar and suprasellar region, which is of heterogeneous intensity inside, due to the presence of bleeding data associated at the sediment-liquid level, which in T1 (a), T2 (b) and FLAIR (c and d) the most rostral and smaller part is hyperintense, and the most caudal part has lower signal intensity. In the sagittal T2-FLAIR image (d), a rounded hypointense area is identified in the most ventral and caudal part; In susceptibility sequence, (d) it presents signal deflection in the dependent zone and in the periphery. This image remodels the floor of the sella turcica, contacts and displaces the pituitary stalk, optic chiasm, hypothalamus, floor of the third ventricle and vascular tracts of the circle of Willis (f). With dimensions of 21x21x26 mm in the rostrocaudal, laterolateral and dorsoventral axes. The blue arrows show the hemorrhages areas.

Figure 2: (a) Histologically features showing necrosis, hemorrhage with cholesterol crystals, and inflammation and giant multinucleated cells are observed. (b) Neoplastic cells are observed among cholesterol clefts and in © observed lymphocytic inflammation with macrophages and hemosiderophages (H&Ex200).

Immunohistochemical reaction sample positive for synaptophysin corresponding to neoplastic cells in (d). CD68 was strongly positive in macrophages and multinucleated giant cells in (e) and in (f). The blue arrows show the multinucleated giant cells.

DISCUSSION

In addition, the limited reporting of sellar xanthogranulomas cases and the absence of characteristic images variety these entities difficult to distinguish from other cystic lesions of the sellar region, such as AdaPC, Rathke's cleft cysts (RCC), Including other pituitary tumors like as arachnoid cysts, epidermoid cysts, and dermoid cysts as well as pituitary hypophysitis (PH).^[7]

Nishioka et al.^[7] studied the endocrinological and radiological characteristics of xanthogranulomas associated with PA. They identified 5 patients (2.2%) with a notable xanthogranulomatous reaction amongst 231 consecutive cases of pituitary adenoma, and just 5 patients showed anterior pituitary insufficiencies. Suggesting the existence of a reactive process in which adenomatous cells could trigger a xanthogranulomatous response, an inflammatory reaction characterized by the presence of lipid-laden macrophages, probably following apoplexy. In a series of the 643 patients with sellar or parasellar tumors Rahmani R, et al.^[8] just found only 4 patients (0.6%) with histologically of xanthogranulomas and Amano K et al.^[2] Reported the pathological characteristics of 7 cases of sellar xanthogranuloma and observed components of Rathke's cleft cyst in 6 of 7 cases.

Even though the differences are determined by histological study, imaging studies are still the first tool that suggests these pathologies, radiologically, these lesions have been reported as cystic lesions, with heterogeneous intensity on MRI. The tumors appeared isointense to hyperintense on T1WI, and the intensity varied from hypointense to hyperintense on T2WI. Following gadolinium-DTPA (diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid) administration, enhancement has usually significant and heterogeneous imaging.^[7] The radiological differential diagnosis includes craniopharyngioma with rupture of cysts structure^[9] and Rathke's cyst and granulomatous hypophysitis.^[10]

Furthermore, a craniopharyngioma cyst can undergo with a spontaneous rupture and can be divided into three subtypes: cyst rupture associated with chemical meningitis; cyst rupture not associated with chemical meningitis; and asymptomatic rupture.^[8] It develops due to the presence of cholesterol crystals in cyst fluid (oil machinery fluid) secreted by the squamous epithelium lining of the cyst and its radiological characteristics are indistinguishable from PA.^[8]

Histologically, the XG is characterized by cholesterol clefts, lymphoplasmacytic infiltrates, marked hemosiderin deposits, fibrosis, multinucleated giant cells around cholesterol clefts, eosinophilic granular necrotic debris, and accumulation of macrophages, with leakage, rupture, or hemorrhage. It is proposed that progressive accumulation of hemosiderin pigment in the lesion, perhaps began by the multiple episodes of bleeding, could account for the transition of at least some cases of XH to XG or rupture of Rathke's cleft cysts (RCC)^[10], and in AdaCPs.^[7,8]

It is well known XG shares some clinical and histological characteristics with other entities, especially with AdaCp and RCC, however, there are differences that allow them to be distinguished and a correct diagnosis to be established.

AdaCP is a benign World Health Organization (WHO) grade I tumors, partially cystic epithelial neoplasm of the suprasellar or sellar region, there are commonly two histological subtypes of craniopharyngiomas: adamantinomatous and papillary.^[11] AdaCP subtype, is one of the sellar neoplasms that can have degenerative changes, such as cystification, dystrophic calcification, and xanthogranuloma reaction that may be due to oil machinery fluid (OMF) activity or secretion.^[5] Normally AdaCP is composed of a section that is solid and cystic. The first one may appear well circumscribed with cords, lobules, nodules, and trabeculae of well differentiated squamous epithelium bordered by a columnar epithelium. These nests of squamous epithelium are surrounded by loose aggregates of squamous epithelium. The cystic part has a yellow-brown, cholesterol-rich fluid; nodules of plump, anucleate squamous cells (ghost cells) and wet keratin which represent desquamated cells that form large, pale, eosinophilic masses that occasionally contain calcium.^[11]

XG reaction of craniopharyngioma, consisting of cholesterol clefts, macrophages, chronic inflammatory infiltrates, necrotic debris, and hemosiderin deposits, has been traditionally considered a hallmark of the adamantinomatous variant, even in the absence of epithelium. Paulus W el al.^[5] suggested that xanthogranuloma (cholesterol granuloma) of the sellar region was a clinically and pathologically distinct from the classical adamantinomatous craniopharyngioma.^[12] Cholesterol cleft's reaction is thought to develop as a secondary reaction to hemorrhage or tissue necrosis (in pituitary adenomas due to apoplexy), or to keratinization as well as OMF (in AdaCP).^[12]

RCC is a benign pathology with cystic lesions encapsulated in a membrane of generally mucoid content microscopically, the cyst wall columnar ciliated epithelium with goblet cells with variable fragments of pituitary tissue, squamous metaplasia and xanthogranulomatous reaction.^[13]

Cystic content is also usefully to guide us in determining the type of injury, for example mucinous material (seen in RCC), cholesterol-rich fluid (in AdaCP), necrotic material (in XH), keratohyaline layer and dry flaky keratins (in epidermoid cysts, and dermoid cysts). The grumous yellowish material which containing giant cells, macrophages, cholesterol clefts and debris^[7] corresponding to a necrotic material observed during surgery could be a very important finding and should not be confused with the OMF of craniopharyngiomas, nor with caseous material from tuberculosis lesions; in this case, the surgeons reported the release of cheesy-looking material.^[14,15]

Pathologically, epithelial cells of PA or Pitnet and XGC are observed and positive immunoreaction for Syn, CroA, ACTH, GH, PRL, LH and TSH and above all, cholesterol clefts, hemosiderin deposits, macrophages (CD68+), giant multinucleated cells (CD68+), chronic inflammatory infiltrates (CD45+) and fibrous proliferation(vimentin+) are identified.^[14,15]

Another pathology that must be differentiated from XSR Is the Inflammation of the pituitary gland which can occur in a variety of primary or secondary disorders. Idiopathic granulomatous hypophysitis is a rare inflammatory disease of the pituitary gland that can closely mimic a PA clinic-radiologically^[14] as well as in Tuberculosis, sarcoidosis, Wegener's granulomatosis, Langerhans cell histiocytosis, and syphilis lined out by suitable tests.^[14,16,17]

As mentioned hypophysitis (PH) is classified into a primary and secondary disease. Xanthomatous hypophysitis is one of the rare types of primary hypophysitis and histologically, it shows pituitary tissue exchanged by inflammatory infiltrate made up of foamy histiocytes grouped in sheets together with lymphoplasmacytic infiltrate. Disseminated areas of fibrosis, hyalinization, and congested and sclerosed blood vessels should be observed.^[16,17] PH may be due to autoimmune or secondary to systemic diseases or infections and based on the

histopathological findings PH is classified into lymphocytic, granulomatous, xanthomatous, mixed forms (lymphogranulomatous, or xanthogranulomatous, necrotizing and Immunoglobulin- G4 (IgG4) plasmacytic types.^[17] Also may occur as a secondary to a reactive degenerative response to an epithelial lesion such as CPs, RCC, or PA; or even within the context of multiorgan involvement related to conditions such as tuberculosis, sarcoidosis, or Erdheim-Chester disease (ECD).^[18] It is a rare multiple system histiocytosis that is characterized pathologically by xanthogranulomatous infiltrates and radiologically by symmetrical sclerosis of long bones.^[18] Pituitary apoplexy (PA) is a clinical syndrome produced by acute hemorrhage or infarction of the pituitary gland and is characterized by the sudden onset of severe headache, visual impairment, ophthalmoplegia and altered mental status. The incidence of PA in patients with pituitary adenoma is approximately 2–7%. Histologically it is noted hemorrhagic infarction, despite extensive tumor necrosis, residual fibrosis, and hemosiderin.^[19] In our case we observed extensive necrosis and cholesterol crystals between them.

In this case, the patient underwent surgical resection; The tumor was removed by endoscopic transsphenoidal endonasal surgery, which has proven to be the most effective therapy for this type of tumor.^[20] Therefore, a complete evaluation, counting clinical, radiological, and histopathological correlation, is needed to establish a definitive diagnosis with a good prognosis.

CONCLUSION

We present a case of a 55-year-old man who began with visual alterations and hypothyroidism and was diagnosed with hypothyroid adenoma and in the histological study showed extensive necrosis and cholesterol crystals with foci of adenoma cells, Suggesting apoplexy changes. Sellar and parasellar tumors such as XSR, RCC, AdaCP or PH may have similar clinical features and radiological findings and unfortunately these pathologies have a lack of a gold standard for an appropriate diagnosis for that reason until a more definitive method is developed, tumors in the sellar region, specially xanthogranulomas should be aware of their existence.

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